

A Study on Financial Performance of Dindigul Urban Co-operative Bank

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Mr. M. Ajai Kather Mohideen

*Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration
MSS Wakf Borad College, Madurai*

Dr. G. Sathish

Assistant Professor, Vijay Insitute of Management

Abstract

Urban cooperatives banks in India are intended to be the instrument for financial inclusion. The essential of UCBs on the India scene has freed the urban and semi-urban areas masses from the clutches of moneylenders and has inculcated a habit of thrift and savings in them. The performance of Tamil Nadu Urban Cooperative Bank had the highest rank with regard to membership, population coverage, borrowings members, loans and advances, deposit mobilization and share capital contribution. The study is based mainly on the secondary data collected from the annual reports of Dindigul UCB for a ten years from 2006-07 to 2015-16. Financial performance of Dindigul UCB was analyzed with respect to efficiency in mobilization, efficiency in deployment, efficiency in NPA and efficiency in operations management. As far as sources of funds are concerned the selected bank mobilizes more through high cost deposits and gives less importance for low cost deposits. This bank failed to deploy medium term, long term loans and the CD ratio is more than 80 per cent. High level ratio reflects the increase of Gross NPA is more than 10 per cent. So the bank affects the profitability and to earn interest income is also low level.

Keywords: Mobilization, Deployment, NPA Management, Operations Management

Introduction

The term Urban Cooperative Banks (UCBs), though not formally defined, refers to primary cooperative banks. At present, 120 Urban Cooperative Banks are functioning in the State of Tamil Nadu (cooperation policy note 2014-15). These UCBs provide banking and credit facilities to the urban and semi urban population. These banks were traditionally centered on communities, localities work place groups. They mobilize deposits from the public and extend credit facilities to small traders, artisans and persons belonging to middle income group for various purposes like housing, business, education, consumer and other non farm sector activities. As on 28.2.2013, the total deposits outstanding in urban cooperative banks is Rs. 5140.46 crore (policy note 2013-14). During 2014-15, these urban banks have disbursed a sum of Rs.5975.39 crores as loan benefiting 1412225 persons (Cooperation policy note 2014-15). The urban cooperatives Banks are expected to lend not less than 60 per cent of their total advances to the priority sector. Besides, it will be ensured that atleast 25 per cent of the priority sector lending shall be disbursed to the weaker sections of community.

Analysis of the Study

Performance of any institution can be evaluated through financial analysis which refers to the analytical study of financial statements which reflect the state of affairs of an organization at a given point of time as well as its financial performance over a period of time. Thus, there is a need to analyze the financial statements by determining the relationship between two figures. This is ascertained by a technique called Ratio Analysis which expresses the numerical relationship between two accounting figures. It is a powerful device to analyze and interpret the financial health of a firm. This not only helps management in decision making and control but also serves as a useful tool for all concerned with the firm.

Hence, the present study is intended to evaluate the financial performance of Dindigul Urban Cooperative Bank (DGL UCB)

Objectives of the Study

1. To analyze the performance of Mobilization of resources by Dindigul UCB
2. To analyze the performance of Deployment of resources by Dindigul UCB
3. To analyze the level of efficiency in NPA Management by Dindigul UCB
4. To analyze the level of Operations Management by Dindigul UCB.

Methodology

The study is based on both the primary data were collected from bank managing director, manager, employees and secondary data collected from annual audit report of Dindigul UCB for ten years from 2006-07 to 2015-16. Financial performance of Dindigul Urban Cooperative Bank was analyzed with respect to efficiency in mobilization, efficiency in deployment, efficiency in NPA management and efficiency in operations.

Efficiency in Mobilization

Efficiency in Mobilization of fund is a most importance to any banking institution as the cost of fund being a critical component in the profitability, is determined by it. It is more significant in the case of co-operative banks as it reflects the member's participation in the organization, level of dependency of borrowed fund and ability to mop up rural savings. Even though there are number of ratios to check the efficiency in mobilization the following are taken for the purpose of study

1. Owned fund to Borrowed fund Ratio
2. Deposit Mix
3. Deposits to Working Capital Ratio
4. Low cost deposit to Total Deposit Ratio

Ratio of Owned fund to Borrowed fund

The owned funds consists of paid-up capital, reserve fund, other reserves, etc. and the borrowed funds consisting of various types of deposits and borrowing from banking institutions, other agencies, etc. This ratio shows the relationship between owned fund and borrowed funds of the bank indicates the relative stake of owners as well as creditors in the institution. It is more significant in a co-operative institution as it shows the level of participation of members. It has to be optimized as a higher ratio can bring a higher profit but create solvency risk.

Table 1.1 Ratio of Owned fund to Borrowed fund**(Rs in Lakhs)**

Year	Owned fund	Borrowed fund	Ratio	Growth rate
2006-07	131.75	1141.00	11.54	-
2007-08	118.81	1150.02	10.33	-89.67
2008-09	113.62	1345.99	8.43	-91.57
2009-10	111.07	1365.80	8.13	-91.87
2010-11	113.68	1468.21	7.73	-92.27
2011-12	125.12	1700.07	7.35	-92.65
2012-13	130.01	2098.38	6.19	-93.81
2013-14	136.87	2534.29	5.36	-94.64
2014-15	138.45	2778.06	4.98	-95.02
2015-16	140.15	2881.01	4.86	-95.14
CAGR	0.62	9.70	-8.28	-

The above table 1.1 shows that the respective share of owners and outsiders stake in the total funds of Dindigul UCB reveals that it has come down from 11.54 per cent to 4.86 with an overall negative growth of -8.28 per cent. This is because the growth of owned fund was not incommensurate with the rate of growth in borrowed funds. This shows that the laxity of the bank in enlarging the membership base and also its inability.

Deposit mix of Dindigul UCB

Deposit mix is the combined portion of fixed deposit, savings deposit and current deposit. This type of deposit mix reflects the quality of deposits and have direct implication on the interest spread and hence on the profitability of the bank. Suitable marketing strategy should with appropriate saving schemes is too developed. The strategy should include identification of potential depositors and ascertaining their economic needs. For identifying the potential depositors, the bank managers should obtain the assistance of the cooperators

Table 1.2 Position of Deposit Mix**(Rs in Lakhs)**

Year	Fixed	Savings	Current	Total	Growth Rate
2006-07	897.83	183.67	59.12	1140.62	-
2007-08	885.40	202.11	62.25	1149.76	0.80
2008-09	1095.57	198.35	51.92	1345.84	17.05
2009-10	998.06	279.10	67.59	1344.75	-0.08
2010-11	1186.36	209.68	71.37	1467.41	9.12
2011-12	1361.34	243.32	71.19	1675.85	14.20
2012-13	1722.99	261.44	105.95	2090.38	24.73
2013-14	2218.56	269.44	39.14	2527.14	20.89
2014-15	2417.92	283.81	67.77	2769.51	9.59
2015-16	2563.14	295.31	71.56	2929.83	5.78
CAGR	11.06	4.86	1.87	9.90	-

The above table 1.2 depicts that the fixed deposit occupies the major position of the deposit mix and the annual growth value of fixed deposit is 11.06 per cent. Another one of deposit mix is savings and current deposit of annual growth value is minimum level. This reflects that the bank concentrate on only high cost deposits so that the bank was earn low level of income.

Ratio of Deposit to working capital

The capital formation of banks takes place through the augmentation of deposits. More deposit mobilization leads to investment in various avenues. It can be measured through the computation of deposit to the working capital to the UCB. Increase in the deposit to working capital ratio indicates the efficiency of societies in the mobilization of deposits

Table 1.3 Ratio of Deposit to Working capital

(Rs in Lakhs)

Year	Deposit	Working capital	Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	1140.62	1272.7	89.62	-
2007-08	1149.76	1268.82	90.61	1.10
2008-09	1345.84	1345.99	99.98	10.34
2009-10	1344.75	1476.87	91.05	-8.93
2010-11	1467.41	1581.81	92.76	1.87
2011-12	1675.85	1825.17	91.81	-1.02
2012-13	2090.38	2228.38	93.80	2.16
2013-14	2527.14	2670.29	94.63	0.88
2014-15	2769.51	2916.46	94.96	0.34
2015-16	2929.83	3021.16	96.97	2.11
CAGR	9.90	9.04	0.69	-

The above table 1.3 depicts that the ratio of deposits to working capital have more than 90 per cent during the study period. The annual growth rate of deposit to working capital ratio is only 0.69 per cent. Deposit occupies the major role to working capital. This shows that the bank have the strong base of working capital through deposit.

Low cost Deposit to total Deposit Ratio

Low cost deposits denote those incur minimum interest burden on the bank. Low cost deposits normally refer savings and current deposits. This type of deposit helps to increase the profitability of the bank. The ratio of low cost deposit to total deposit ratio is higher means the bank get the high profit.

Table 1.4 Ratio of Low cost deposit to total Deposit

(Rs in Lakhs)

Year	Current	Deposit	Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	59.12	1140.62	5.18	-
2007-08	62.25	1149.76	5.41	4.44
2008-09	51.92	1345.84	3.85	-28.83
2009-10	67.59	1344.75	5.02	30.38
2010-11	71.37	1467.41	4.86	-3.18

2011-12	71.19	1675.85	4.24	-12.75
2012-13	105.95	2090.38	5.06	19.33
2013-14	39.14	2527.14	1.54	-69.56
2014-15	67.77	2769.51	2.44	58.44
2015-16	71.56	2929.83	2.44	0
CAGR	1.87	9.90	-7.25	-

The above table 1.4 depicts that the ratio of low cost deposits to total deposit had been decreasing trend after the year 2012-13 and the annual growth value is -7.25 negative per cent. The position of current deposits annual growth rate value is only 1.87 per cent. The portion of low cost deposits is the lower value of total deposits. This shows that the bank gets lower interest rate on low cost deposits, which will affect their profitability.

Efficiency in Deployment

Bank gets income by way of returns from effective deployment of funds. More than that, it ensures it's the organized objective of helping the small farmers, small traders, business man and other weaker sections people for the socio economic development. Hence it is examined here. Mobilized funds are normally deployed as loan as well as investments, keeping the liquidity requirement norms. Following are the indicators for this purpose.

1. Loan Mix
2. Credit to Deposit Ratio
3. Loans to Working Capital
4. Secured Loan to total Loan Ratio
5. Un secured Loan to Total Loan Ratio

Loan Mix

A term loan is a combination of short term, medium term and long term loan disbursements were the prime functions of the UCB. This type of advance granted to a business of industrial undertaking to acquire fixed assets (eg. Land, building, plant and machinery, etc) for starting an industry or business unit. Terms loan are also granted against the security of fixed assets to enable the borrowers to meet long term working capital requirements

Table 2.1 Position of Loan mix

(Rs in Lakhs)

Year	Short term loan	Medium term loan	Total	Growth rate
2006-07	731 (66.27)	372 (33.73)	1103 (100)	-
2007-08	761 (74.68)	258 (25.32)	1019 (100)	-7.61
2008-09	917 (81.66)	206 (18.34)	1123 (100)	10.20
2009-10	1268 (90.83)	128 (9.17)	128 (9.17)	24.30
2010-11	1401 (90.44)	148 (9.55)	1549 (100)	10.95
2011-12	1633 (91.28)	156 (8.72)	1789 (100)	15.49

2012-13	1870 (90.51)	196 (9.49)	2066 (100)	15.48
2013-14	1930 (88.25)	257 (11.75)	2187 (100)	5.85
2014-15	1955 (84.05)	371 (15.95)	2326 (100)	6.35
2015-16	2085 (84.24)	390 (15.75)	2475 (100)	6.40
CAGR	11.05	0.47	8.42	-

The above table 2.1 depicts that the position of loan mix had been increasing trend during the study period. The annual growth rate of short term loan is 11.05 per cent and medium term loan is only 0.47 per cent. This shows that the short term loan occupies the major part of loan mix. As per discussion with the bank officials revealed that in the short term loans are attractive where as in the case of medium term loan and the incidence of risk is very high so that the bank itself discouraging it.

Credit to Deposit Ratio

This ratio is defined as the loans and advances outstanding as a percentage to the total deposit balance as on a particular day. The deposits are mobilized for the purpose of giving credit through loans and advances, investment. High ratios indicates the bank have the effective lending and recovery operations. Dependency on external resources is high.

Table 2.2 Ratio of credit to deposit

(Rs in Lakhs)

Year	Credit	Deposit	Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	1103	1140.62	83.81	-
2007-08	1019	1149.76	95.93	14.46
2008-09	1123	1345.84	75.71	-21.07
2009-10	1396	1344.75	83.50	10.28
2010-11	1549	1467.41	95.13	13.92
2011-12	1789	1675.85	106.75	12.21
2012-13	2066	2090.38	98.83	-7.41
2013-14	2187	2527.14	86.54	-12.43
2014-15	2326	2769.51	83.98	-2.95
2015-16	2475	2929.83	84.47	0.58
CAGR	8.42	9.90	0.12	-

The above table 2.2 represents that the position of credit on deposit ratio annual growth rate is 0.12 per cent only. The bank maintains the credit on deposit ratio is below 100 per cent except the year 2012-13. As per RBI norms the CD ratio is not more than 70 per cent of all the UCB. But the dindigul UCB have more than 80 per cent CD ratio of throughout the study period. This shows that the high level of CD ratio is chance to increase of NPA and also affect the profitability.

Loans to Working Capital

Loans to Working Capital Ratio also act as an indicator of the efficiency in turning over the working capital to credit. Higher level of loans to working capital ratio is always favorable. Since the efficiency in deployments of working capital is directly linked with its proportion advanced

as loans, loans to working capital ratio is better criterion for the analysis of efficiency in fund management of the bank.

Table 2.3 Ratio of Loans to working capital**(Rs in Lakhs)**

Year	Loans	Working capital	Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	1103	1272.7	86.66	-
2007-08	1019	1268.82	80.31	-7.32
2008-09	1123	1345.99	83.43	3.88
2009-10	1396	1476.87	94.52	13.29
2010-11	1549	1581.81	97.92	3.59
2011-12	1789	1825.17	98.01	0.09
2012-13	2066	2228.38	92.71	-5.40
2013-14	2187	2670.29	81.90	-11.66
2014-15	2326	2916.46	79.75	-2.62
2015-16	2475	3021.16	81.92	2.72
CAGR	8.42	9.04	-0.56	

The above table 2.3 depicts that the ratio of loans to working capital is more than 80 per cent during the study period and the annual growth rate is -0.56 negative per cent. A comparative analysis of credit with working capital and deposits will reveal the prudent financial management practice of the Dindigul UCB. Effective utilization of lendable resources is assessed by these means.

Secured Loan to Total Loans Ratio

Secured loans are those loans that are protected by an asset or collateral of some sort. Secured loans are usually the best and only way to obtain large amount of money. Higher level of secured loan to total loans ratio indicates the bank attracts the majorly part of secured loan and it is always securable. Since the bank was always secured with amount and the efficiency in fund management of the bank.

Table 2.4 Ratio of secured loan to total Loan**(Rs in Lakhs)**

Year	Secured loan	Total loans	Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	1023	1103	92.75	-
2007-08	945	1019	92.73	-0.02
2008-09	1050	1123	93.49	0.81
2009-10	1324	1396	94.84	1.44
2010-11	1465	1549	94.57	-0.28
2011-12	1712	1789	95.69	1.18
2012-13	1970	2066	95.35	-0.35
2013-14	2091	2187	95.61	0.27
2014-15	2235	2326	96.08	0.49
2015-16	2384	2475	96.34	0.27
CAGR	8.83	8.42	0.43	

The above table 2.4 depicts that the ratio of secured loan to total loan is more than 90 per cent during the study period and the annual growth rate is only 0.43 per cent. The secured loan plays the major role of total loan. This shows that the bank issue more number of secured loan. As per discussion with the bank staffs the secured loan is easy to recover and the bank was not to affecting the NPA.

UN Secured Loan to Total Loans Ratio

Unsecured loans are monetary loans that are not secured against the borrower's asset. Lower level of unsecured loan to total loans ratio indicates that bank attracts very minimum level of unsecured loan. Since the bank have high level of risk and rate of interest is also high.

Table 2.5 Ratio of UN secured loan to total Loan

(Rs in Lakhs)

Year	UN Secured loan	Total loans	Ratio	Growth rate
2006-07	79.99	1103	7.25	-
2007-08	75.20	1019	7.37	1.65
2008-09	73.32	1123	6.52	-11.53
2009-10	73.14	1396	5.23	-19.78
2010-11	82.47	1549	5.32	1.72
2011-12	76.33	1789	4.26	-19.92
2012-13	95.4	2066	4.61	8.21
2013-14	94.70	2187	4.33	-6.07
2014-15	91.40	2326	3.92	-9.46
2015-16	90.75	2475	3.63	-7.39
CAGR	1.31	8.42	-6.68	

The above table 2.5 depicts that the ratio of unsecured loan to total loan had been decreasing trend during the study period and the ratio annual growth value is – 6.68 per cent. The unsecured loan annual growth rate is only 1.31 per cent. The unsecured loan contributes very minimum level of total loan. This shows that the bank was not to concentrate on unsecured loan. These types of unsecured loan have the high level of risk and the bank face the problem of issue to unsecured loan without security.

Efficiency of NPA Management

NPA means a credit facility in respect of which interest and / or installment of principal has remained overdue for a period of more than 90 days. However, the growth of Non Performing Assets (NPAs) as syndrome, though not new to the cooperative banking structure has been causing trouble and confusion to UCBs during recent past. Because NPAs as the percentage to total recoverable funds acts as a constraint on the efficiency of the lending institution and their capacity to borrow funds and lend to eligible members. Inordinate delay in recovery of loans and advances builds up NPAs, which affects UCBs adversely with respect to liquidity. So the bank must follow the efficiency in NPA management the following are taken for the purpose of study:

1. Gross NPA Ratio
2. Net NPA Ratio
3. Secured loan to Gross NPA Ratio
4. Un secured loan to Gross NPA Ratio
5. Provision Ratio

Gross NPA ratio

The Gross NPA is the better indicator than net NPA of the quality of the loan portfolio. Gross NPA is the sum total of all loans that are classified as NPA as per the RBI guidelines as on the balance sheet date. The Gross NPA indicates the quality of credit portfolio of the bank. High gross NPA ratio indicates low quality credit portfolio.

Table 3.1 Gross NPA Ratio**(Rs in Lakhs)**

Year	Gross NPA	Gross Advance	Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	339.00	1103	30.73	-
2007-08	250.00	1020	24.50	-20.27
2008-09	213.00	1123	18.96	-22.61
2009-10	259.00	1396	18.55	-2.162
2010-11	111.00	1549	7.16	-61.40
2011-12	96.00	1789	5.36	-25.13
2012-13	98.00	2067	4.74	-11.56
2013-14	251.00	2187	11.47	141.98
2014-15	278.00	2327	11.94	4.09
2015-16	265.00	2475	10.70	-10.38
CAGR	-2.43	8.42	-10.01	-

The above table 3.1 depicts that the ratio of Gross NPA had been decreasing trend up to the year 2012-13 and the annual growth rate is- 10.01 negative per cent. The Gross NPA of annual growth rate is -2.43 negative growth values. This shows that the bank have the good managing NPA level up to the year 2012-13. The last three years the ratio of gross NPA is high level so the bank must to reduce the NPA and the bank takes immediate recovery action.

Net NPA ratio

The net NPA ratio is the ratio of Net NPA to net advances expressed in terms of percentage. It indicates the degree of riskiness in the credit portfolio of the bank. Net NPA is determined by deducting provisions from gross NPA. As per RBI circular the Urban Cooperatives Banks maintain the Net NPA of less than 3 per cent (RBI/2014-15/26/Cir.No.20/07.01.000/2014-15 Oct 13.2014). High net NPA indicates the existence of highly risky loans in the bank for which no adequate provision had been made.

Table 3.2 Net NPA Ratio**(Rs in Lakhs)**

Year	Net NPA	Net Advance	Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	339.59	882.51	38.48	-
2007-08	225.74	850.76	26.53	-31.05
2008-09	188.81	934.84	20.19	-23.89
2009-10	135.52	1273.91	10.63	-47.35
2010-11	28.55	1464.73	1.95	-81.65
2011-12	10.78	1702.77	0.63	-67.69

2012-13	14.01	1981.25	0.71	12.69
2013-14	151.38	2086.17	7.25	921.12
2014-15	163.08	2211.87	7.37	1.65
2015-16	155.21	2374.87	6.54	-11.26
CAGR	-7.53	10.41	-16.24	-

The above table 3.2 depicts that the ratio of Net NPA had been decreasing trend up to the year 2012-13 after the year the Net NPA was increased and the annual growth value is -16.24 negative per cent. This shows that the bank had well managed of the Net NPA up to the year 2012-13. The bank takes some special efforts to maintain the Net NPA at below 3 per cent in all the future year.

Secured loan NPA ratio

Secured loans usually offer lower rates, higher borrowing limits and longer repayments terms than unsecured loans. As the term implies, a secured loan means you are providing “security” that your loan will be repaid according to the agreed terms and conditions. Its important to remember, if you are unable to repay a secured loan, the lender has resource to the collateral you have pledged and may be able to sell it to pay off the loan. Even though the NPA in secured loan ratio is increase the bank affect the loan of NPA

Table 3.3 NPA of Secured Loan Ratio

(Rs in Lakhs)

Year	NPA Secured loan	Gross NPA	Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	261	339.00	76.99	-
2007-08	176	250.00	70.40	-20.27
2008-09	144	213.00	67.60	-22.61
2009-10	196	259.00	75.67	-2.162
2010-11	51	111.00	45.94	-61.40
2011-12	45	96.00	46.87	-25.13
2012-13	47	98.00	47.95	-11.56
2013-14	189	251.00	75.29	141.98
2014-15	212	278.00	76.25	4.09
2015-16	208	265.00	78.49	-10.38
CAGR	-2.24	-2.43	0.19	-

The above table depicts that the ratio of annual Growth rate of NPA in secured loan only 0.19 per cent and the secured loan of NPA had been decreasing trend up to the year 2012-13. This shows that secured loan occupies the major portion of NPA during the study period. So the bank takes some legal action to reduce the NPA.

UN Secured loan NPA ratio

UN secured loans are opposite to secured loan and include things like credit card purchases, education loans, or personal (Signature) loans. Lenders take more of a risk by making such loan, with no property or assets to recovery in case of default, which is considerably higher. The ratio of NPA in Unsecured loan is higher means the bank face high level risk.

Table 3.4 NPA of UN Secured Loan Ratio**(Rs in Lakhs)**

Year	UN Secured loan advance	Gross NPA	Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	78.93	339.00	23.28	-
2007-08	74.06	250.00	29.62	27.23
2008-09	69.65	213.00	32.67	10.29
2009-10	63.14	259.00	24.37	-25.40
2010-11	61.47	111.00	55.37	127.20
2011-12	52.33	96.00	54.51	-1.55
2012-13	52.45	98.00	53.46	-1.92
2013-14	62.71	251.00	24.98	-53.27
2014-15	66.46	278.00	23.88	-4.40
2015-16	57.02	265.00	21.51	-9.92
CAGR	-3.20	-2.43	-0.79	-

The above table shows that the ratio of NPA in unsecured loan annual growth rate is -0.79 negative per cent and unsecured loan NPA had been erotic trend during the study period. In the year 2010-11 the value of growth rate is 127.20 high. This shows that the unsecured loan was not affecting the NPA in Dindigul UCB.

Provision Ratio

It is the ratio of total provisions held in respect of gross NPAs of the bank. It indicates the degree of safety measures adopted of safety measures adopted by the banks. It has direct bearing on profitability of the bank. If the provisions ratio is less it indicates that the bank has not made adequate provisions for problematic loan assets. The upward movement of the provision ratio indicates that the bank is adopting adequate measures for the future loan losses

Table 3.5 Provisioning Ratio**(Rs in Lakhs)**

Year	Provisions	Gross NPAs	Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	203.13	339.00	59.92	-
2007-08	203.13	250.00	81.25	35.59
2008-09	203.13	213.00	95.36	17.36
2009-10	203.13	259.00	78.42	-17.76
2010-11	203.13	111.00	183.01	133.37
2011-12	203.13	96.00	211.59	15.61
2012-13	203.13	98.00	207.27	-2.04
2013-14	203.13	251.00	80.92	-60.95
2014-15	203.13	278.00	73.06	-9.71
2015-16	203.13	265.00	76.65	4.91
CAGR	0.00	-2.45	2.49	-

The above table shows that the provisioning ratio of annual growth value is 2.49 per cent. In the year 2010-11 to 2012-13 the bank maintain the excess provisions and the ratio value is high level. This shows that the bank have the safe with the provisions level of during the study period.

Efficiency in operations

Having seen the efficiency of sources and uses of funds separately, the reflection of these in the operations needed a close look as the efficiency of sources and uses of funds will reflect in the profitability. Even though the co-operatives are service motive, surplus is also needed for their existence and growth. Hence an attempt is made to examine the efficiency in operation of Dindgul UCB by a disaggregated analysis of the profitability of bank. To find out the operational efficiency the following ratios are used:

1. Spread Ratio
2. Burden Ratio
3. Profitability Ratio
4. Manpower Expense to Total Expense

Spread Ratio

Spread ratio can be expressed as a relationship between interest spread and total funds of the bank. Spread is the difference between interest income and interest expenses. Investment, Loans and advances is the major source of Interest income in the banking sector. Interest expenses are expenses on fund acquisition and represent the cost of fund. Interest on deposit and interest paid on borrowings are the main reasons of interest expenses. This type of ratio shows the efficiency in lending operations, higher ratio is preferable since it is possible only when the interest received on loans are more than interest paid on deposits and its borrowings.

Table 4.1 Spread Ratio of DGL UCB

(Rs in Lakhs)

Year	Interest income	Interest EXP	Spread	Total Fund	Spread Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	154.41	77.44	76.97	1272.75	6.04	-
2007-08	148.45	78.11	70.34	1268.82	5.54	-0.08
2008-09	144.98	93.57	51.41	1345.99	3.81	-0.31
2009-10	163.74	112.89	50.85	1476.87	3.44	-0.09
2010-11	151.35	99.40	51.95	1581.81	3.28	-0.04
2011-12	307.36	129.37	177.99	1825.17	9.75	1.97
2012-13	302.56	189.74	112.82	2228.38	5.06	-0.48
2013-14	346.97	225.02	121.95	2670.29	4.56	-0.09
2014-15	387.12	241.39	145.73	2916.46	4.99	0.09
2015-16	399.15	262.47	136.68	3021.16	4.52	-0.09
CAGR	9.96	13.03	5.99	9.04	-	-

The above table 4.1 exhibits the spread ratio of Dinidgul UCB had been erotic trend during the year 2006-07 to 2015-16. The annual growth rate of interest expenses is 13.03 per cent. The amount of interest income is high compare to interest expenses and the spread value is always positive. This shows that the bank earns interest income through loans and advance, investments.

Burden Ratio

The burden ratio is relationship between the Non interest income and Noninterest Expenses. This Non- interest income is income other than interest income like commission on services provided to customers, exchange and brokerage subsidies etc. The non interest expenses are expenses like rent,

taxes, insurance charges, advertising charges, postage and telephone charges. Burden ratio is the ratio of burden to working fund of the bank. A lower ratio is preferable because reducing burden will improve the profitability of the bank.

Table 4.2 Burden Ratio of DGL UCB**(Rs in lakhs)**

Year	Non-interest income	Non Interest Expenses	Spread	Total Fund	Burden Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	14.47	40.35	-25.88	1272.75	2.03	-
2007-08	16.73	40.04	-23.31	1268.82	1.82	-0.10
2008-09	10.33	53.11	-42.78	1345.99	3.17	0.74
2009-10	15.95	62.54	-46.59	1476.87	3.15	-0.01
2010-11	5.25	35.94	-30.69	1581.81	1.94	-0.3
2011-12	5.76	40.8	-35.04	1825.17	1.91	-0.01
2012-13	6.93	47.12	-40.19	2228.38	1.80	-0.05
2013-14	10.86	34.34	-23.48	2670.29	0.87	-0.51
2014-15	6.92	33.61	-26.69	2916.46	0.91	0.04
2015-16	8.5	33.72	-25.22	3021.16	0.83	-0.09
CAGR	-5.18	-1.78	-	9.04	-	-

The above table 4.2 reveals that the value of spread is negative trend at all over the year. The burden ratio is not only low but also fluctuating. The annual growth rate is negative per cent of both noninterest income and noninterest expenses. This shows that the bank have the minimum level of non-interest income compare to non-interest expenses. So the bank must to concentrate on Non-interest income this helps to reduce the burden level of the Dindigul UCB

Profitability Ratio

Profit as expressed in absolute terms makes no much sense in the performance analysis and may not indicate whether the banks operations are satisfactory or not. It is necessary to relate profit and working funds for analyzing operational efficiency and there by profitability of the bank.

Table 4.3 Profitability Ratio of DGL UCB**(Rs in Lakhs)**

Year	Spread Ratio	Burden Ratio	Profitability Ratio	Growth Rate
2006-07	6.04	2.03	4.01	-
2007-08	5.54	1.82	3.72	-0.07
2008-09	3.81	3.17	0.64	-0.82
2009-10	3.44	3.15	0.29	-0.54
2010-11	3.28	1.94	1.34	3.62
2011-12	9.75	1.91	7.84	4.85
2012-13	5.06	1.80	3.26	-0.58
2013-14	4.56	0.87	3.69	0.13
2014-15	4.99	0.91	4.08	0.10
2015-16	4.52	0.83	3.69	-0.09
CAGR	-2.86	-8.56	-0.83	-

The above table 4.3 shows that the profitability ratio had been fluctuating trend during the study period and this ratio is always is below 4 per cent. In the year 2006-07 to 2010-11 the profitability ratio is low due to the position of NPA is high and the recovery performance is low.

Manpower Expenses Ratio

Manpower expenses being the major item of non interest expenditure need an examination at this point. Hence it is attempted here. Manpower expenses denote the expenses incurred by the bank to maintain their employees. It includes staff salary, bonus, leave salary, DA, staff PF contribution, and staff welfare fund contribution.

Table 4.4 Manpower Expenses Ratio of DGL UCB

(Rs in Lakhs)

Year	Man power Expenses	Total Expenses	Ratio	Growth
2006-07	37.09	154.88	23.94	-
2007-08	38.07	156.22	24.36	0.01
2008-09	40.46	187.14	21.62	-0.11
2009-10	50.35	265.78	18.94	-0.12
2010-11	44.35	179.69	24.68	0.30
2011-12	42.43	212.67	19.95	-0.19
2012-13	37.70	274.56	13.73	-0.31
2013-14	54.11	313.47	17.26	0.26
2014-15	37.81	312.81	12.08	-0.30
2015-16	39.93	336.12	11.87	-0.02
CAGR	0.74	8.11	-7.48	-

The above table 4.4 reveals that the ratio of man power expenses to total expenses had been decreasing trend during the study period and the annual growth rate is -7.48 negative per cent. This shows that the manpower expenses are not affecting the total expenses in dindigul UCB.

Conclusion and recommendations

The study which is to analyzed the financial performance of the Dindigul Urban Cooperative Bank reveals that there is a need for strong intervention by the professionals. As far as source of funds concerned the selected bank mobilizes more through high cost of deposits and gives less importance for low cost of deposit. This bank failed to deploy medium term, long term loans and the CD ratio is more than 80 per cent. High level ratio reflects the increase of Gross NPA is more than 10 per cent. So the bank affects the profitability and to earn interest income is also low level. However, it's hearting to note that the bank maintains the statutory requirements.

The analyses lead us to recommend the following action plan for the selected cooperative bank.